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Towards a Sustainable Blue Tourism in the Mediterranean

Regional Governance, Environmental Management
and Sustainable Recovery of the Mediterranean Coastal
and Maritime Tourism

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1 Introduccion

This report is part of a global initiative aiming to improve the **environmental Governance** of Coastal and Marine Tourism around the **World Regional Seas**, launched by eco-union and **IDDRI** in 2019. This study is an extension of the flagship report **Towards a Sustainable Blue Tourism**¹ published in 2019. Focusing on the Mediterranean, this report explores the current **State of play** of coastal and marine tourism in the region, reviews the socio-economic impact related to **COVID-19 pandemic** and highlights **opportunities for a better management** of coastal and marine tourism based on inclusive, participatory and long-term environmental policies and strategies.

¹ eco-union (2019): [Towards a Sustainable Blue Tourism around World Marine Regions](#)

2 The Mediterranean basin, a vulnerable ecosystem under growing stress

The Mediterranean region counts a **vast diversity** of geographic, economic, cultural and demographic profiles. All mediterranean countries benefit from mild climatic conditions that make them a sought-after travel spot. **Tourism has become a central part of their economies**, especially in the coastal areas. However mass tourism has a severe **impact on natural, cultural and human ecosystems**, bringing positive socio-economic benefits but also damaging and depleting vulnerable and limited resources. While a number of national and international environmental policies regulate the sector, the region remains under high stress due to rising environmental pollution, land-use change, biodiversity losses and climate change impacts².

2 UNEP/MAP, Plan Bleu (2020): State of Environment and Development in the Mediterranean.

2.1 Tourism as a major economic sector

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MEDITERRANEAN REGION³

States: Albania, Algeria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Cyprus, Egypt, France, Greece, Israel, Italy, Lebanon, Libya, Malta, Monaco, Montenegro, Morocco, Slovenia, Spain, Syria, Tunisia, Turkey, Palestine.	Population: 505 million (2019)	Geographical sea extension: 2.6 million km ² (0.82% world's ocean surface)	Coastline: 46,000 kilometers Marine fauna: 900 species (IUCN)
	Coastal population: 160-170 million (around 1/3 of total population)		

Source: IUCN⁴, World Bank, WTTC

The Mediterranean region, welcoming annually more than 350 million national and international tourists, is one of the most popular destinations in the world. **Tourism** accounts for 11.5% of employment in total. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the tourism sector was in full expansion, tourism flows having grown over 75% since 1995, and projected to reach 626 million by 2025 according to the UN World Tourism Organization (WTO).

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONTRIBUTION OF TRAVEL AND TOURISM IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

Average total contribution of tourism to GDP: 12,9%	Average total contribution of tourism to employment: 13,3%	Average Growth of Tourism in 2019: 5,7%
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Source: 2019 data, WTTC⁵

The regional repartition of Mediterranean tourism flows is characterized by a significant unbalance, both in terms of tourism flows and economic benefits. Indeed, the North-West of the Mediterranean concentrates 64% of International Tourism Arrivals (France with 84 million, Spain with 65 million, and Italy with 48 million), while the South-East Mediterranean represents only 17% of ITA, the North-East

Mediterranean 14% of ITA and the South-West Mediterranean 5%⁶ of ITA. Furthermore, while the total contribution of tourism in the Mediterranean region was estimated at 901 billion dollars in 2015, only 58 billion dollars benefitted to North African countries⁷.

³ Aggregates and average data taking into account contracting parties to the [Barcelona Convention](#). ⁴ [IUCN web site](#). ⁵ WTTC (2019): [Economic Impact Report](#) - Data available for Egypt, France, Italy, Greece, Morocco, Spain, Turkey, Tunisia. ⁶ Petrick, K.; Fosse, J.; Lammens, H. & Fiorucci, F. (2017): [Blue economy in the Mediterranean](#). UfM. ⁷ WTTC (2017): [Travel & Tourism Economic Impact North Africa 2017](#).

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MEDITERRANEAN INTERNATIONAL TOURIST ARRIVALS TREND (1995-2019)

In the last ten years, some Southern Mediterranean countries, such as **Egypt** and **Turkey**, have seen significant growth in coastal tourism, with governments encouraging the private sector to develop important tourism projects in coastal areas⁹. Tourism however remains unstable and volatile given that this sector is very sensitive to external and internal turbulences. Simultaneous crises such as social conflicts and political turmoil, terrorism

and insecurity, economic slowdown and unemployment, as well as climate change and environmental degradation, and now a global pandemic, negatively affect tourism flows¹⁰.

2.2. Mass tourism concentrated in coastal areas

The Mediterranean Sea is the largest of the semi-closed European seas, with a basin area covering almost 2.6 million km². Its 46.000 km of coastline¹¹ is shared between 22 countries of similar environmental, climatic, historical and cultural ties. Yet significant differences of economic contexts, population growth rates, humanitarian crises and climate change impacts, contribute to creating a rift between the Northern and Southern shores of the Mediterranean region. Spread across three continents, it is home to about **500 million people**, of which approximately a third lives in coastal areas¹², where tourism is concentrated,

leading to urban sprawl and artificialization of the coast. Tourism is the main economic sector in the Mediterranean region, being the world's principal regional tourist destination¹³ with **30% of the global tourism flow**.

⁸ World Tourism Organization (2020): *UNWTO Tourism Barometer*. ⁹ CIOB (2016): *Egyptian developers plan \$1.7bn tourist resort on Mediterranean coast - News*. ¹⁰ Fosse, J. & Le Tellier, J. (2017) *Sustainable Tourism in the Mediterranean: State of Play and Strategic Direction*. Plan Bleu. ¹¹ EEA - UNEP/MAP (2014): *Horizon 2020 Mediterranean report Toward shared environmental information systems*. ¹² EEA (2015): *Mediterranean Sea region briefing - The European environment — state and outlook 2015*. ¹³ UNWTO (2018): *Tourism Highlights: 2018 Edition*.

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CONCENTRATION OF TOURISM IN MEDITERREAN COASTS

International
Tourist
Arrivals (2017):International
Tourist
Arrivals
Med Coast:

Source: eco-union (2019)

2.3 Fragile Biodiversity hotspots around touristic places

The Mediterranean sea hosts between 7% and 9% of the world's marine biodiversity of which 20-30% are endemic species. While it benefits from strong legal protection with 1,231 marine protected areas covering 179,798 km²¹⁴, 51% of native marine fish species and subspecies in the Mediterranean are in danger of extinction and 22 species (4%) are listed as near threatened¹⁵. Pressures contributing to the loss of habitats include unsustainable exploitation of resources, pollution, climate change, eutrophication and invasive marine species¹⁶. Biodiversity is fundamental to the Mediterranean economy, with benefits derived from **ecosystem services**

estimated over €26 billion a year. Of these, more than two-thirds come from tourism and value derived from nature¹⁷.

The CEPF¹⁸ has identified 533 **Key Biodiversity Areas** (KBAs) for the 16 countries and territories in the Mediterranean Basin Hotspot covered by the ecosystem profile, and 1,150 KBAs for the hotspot as a whole. KBAs represent an agenda for conservation of the most threatened biodiversity but they are not necessarily protected areas. The analysis shows that, of 438 KBAs present in countries with reliable data, only 189 (43%) are entirely or partly within protected areas.

¹⁴ MedPAN and. al. (2016): *The 2016 status of Marine Protected Areas in the Mediterranean: Main findings*. ¹⁵ IUCN website. ¹⁶ Coll, M. and al., (2010): *The Biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: Estimates, Patterns, and Threats*. ¹⁷ Claudet & Fraschetti (2010) ; UNEP/MAP (2020): *State of Environment and Development* ; MedPAN and al. (2016) ; Interreg Mediterranean Sustainable Tourism ; WWF (2017). ¹⁸ CEPE (2017): *Ecosystem Profile Mediterranean Basin Biodiversity Hotspot*.

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KEY BIODIVERSITY AREAS (KBA) IN THE MEDITERRANEAN BASIN

Source: CEPF (2017)

2.4 An immature and unbalanced regional governance

In the Mediterranean, the main regional multilateral frameworks related to environmental, marine and tourism governance are the **Barcelona Convention** (for all Riparian countries), the **EU policies** (for Northern Mediterranean countries) and the **Union for the Mediterranean** (UfM) initiatives (for all Mediterranean countries), as described below.

2.4.1 Barcelona Convention and its Mediterranean Action Plan

The **Mediterranean Action Plan** (UNEP, 1975) and the **Barcelona Convention** (1976) are ratified by 22 Mediterranean riparian countries, as an intergovernmental agreement aimed at protecting the regional coastal and marine environment

VERSION AND PROTOCOLS	RELEVANCE TO TOURISM	SPECIFIC TO SUSTAINABLE TOURISM
Convention (1976)¹⁹	- Tourism is not mentioned · Article 5 and 6 aim at preventing pollution from ships (including cruise ships).	NO
Convention (1995)²⁰	Tourism is not mentioned	NO
Protocol for the Protection against Pollution from Land-Based Sources and Activities (1980)²¹	Identifies tourism as an economic activity to regard when setting priorities for action plans.	Recognises the environmental pressures of the tourism industry.

¹⁹ UNEP : Mediterranean Action Plan ; Convention for the protection of the Mediterranean Sea against pollution (1976). ²⁰ UNEP : Mediterranean Action Plan ; Amendments to the Convention for the protection of the mediterranean sea against pollution (1995). ²¹ Barcelona Convention and Protocols.

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VERSION AND PROTOCOLS	RELEVANCE TO TOURISM	SPECIFIC TO SUSTAINABLE TOURISM
Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) in the Mediterranean (2008) ²²	Integrates article 9 on Tourism, sporting and recreational activities.	(I) Encourage sustainable coastal tourism that preserves coastal ecosystems, natural resources, cultural heritage and landscapes; (II) Promote specific forms of coastal tourism, including cultural, rural and ecotourism, while respecting the traditions of local populations; (III) Regulate or, where necessary, prohibit the practice of various sporting and recreational activities, including recreational fishing and shellfish extraction.
Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production in the Mediterranean (2016) ²³	It promotes a specific regional action plan for sustainable tourism with several objectives.	3.1: Reduce environmental impacts of tourism (...); 3.2: Promote regulatory, legislative and financial measures (on) sustainable consumption and production in tourism (...) 3.3: (...) support sustainable destinations and green tourism services (...)
Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) 2016-2025 (2016) ²⁴	Tourism appears in several objectives and actions of the MSSD, in particular Objectives 2 (rural development) and 3 (cities).	2.4.3. Sustainable rural tourism 3.1.2. Ensure legally-binding instruments for tourism development

2.4.2 European Policies and regional initiatives

The most important initiatives at the European Union level to protect the marine and coastal environment are the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive** (MSFD, 2008) aiming to achieve **Good Environmental Status** (GES) of the

EU's marine waters by 2020²⁵ and the Directive for **Maritime Spatial Planning** (MSP, 2014)²⁶. In the tourism sector, the European Union also launched an **Ecolabel**²⁷ initiative to help consumers to choose environmental certified products and services.

WestMED initiative ²⁸

The purpose of the WestMed Initiative, a project supported by the European Commission and the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM), is to foster sustainable blue growth and jobs, improve safety and security and preserve ecosystems and biodiversity in the Western Mediterranean region. This aims to be achieved through coordination and cooperation among the relevant countries, both EU members and not: Algeria, France, Italy, Libya, Malta, Mauritania, Morocco, Portugal, Spain and Tunisia.

²² UNEP: Mediterranean Action Plan ; Protocol on Integrated Coastal Zone Management in the Mediterranean (2008). ²³ UNEP: Mediterranean Action Plan ; Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production in the Mediterranean (2017) ²⁴ UNEP: Mediterranean Action Plan ; Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (2016). ²⁵ EU Coastal and Marine Policy : Marine Strategy Framework Directive. ²⁶ EC: Maritime spatial planning. ²⁷ EC : EU Ecolabel. ²⁸ WestMED.

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Other policies relevant to tourism development in the Mediterranean include initiatives in transport, consumer protection and visa allowances. The European Union - for whom tourism represents, directly or indirectly, **10% of GDP** - has a significant role supporting socio-economic development in member states. Its targets are multifold: guaranteeing safe, competitive, and technologically up-to-date economy, including in the tourism sector.

Moreover, tourism development in Europe is also influenced by the non-environmental regulatory frameworks of the European Commission. The EU main mobility mechanism is the **Schengen Area**, which abolishes controls at the EU's internal borders, thus facilitating free internal movement of people. The **Service in the**

Internal Market Directive (also called Bolkestein Directive), aiming at establishing a single market for services within the European Union, and the **Digital Services Act**, are also contributing to the rise of the services and products in the tourism sector. Both policies have a high influence on the regional and local regulation of tourism activities such as the short-term rentals commercialised through digital platforms like Airbnb or Booking.

MAIN ENVIRONMENTAL AND TOURISM GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORKS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN

INTERNATIONAL FRAMEWORKS	DESCRIPTION	IMPACT ON TOURISM	RELEVANT POLICIES & REGULATIONS
Barcelona convention	The Barcelona Convention commits parties to prevent, reduce and eliminate marine pollution and improve sustainability of the Mediterranean basin	Indirect: conservation and prevention of the marine ecosystem.	Mediterranean Action plan (1995), Barcelona Convention (1995), SCP AP (2016), MSSD (2016)
EU environmental and climate policies	The EU Environmental Policies and legislation apply to air and water quality, and promotion of low-carbon economy at the regional level.	Indirect: restriction over coastal development, wastewater management, emission control (cruises) waste management for ships, protection of biodiversity and definition of protected areas.	Natura 2000 Directive (1992), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008), Port Waste Reception Facilities Directive (2000), Maritime Spatial Planning Directing (2014), MRV Regulation (2015), Sulphur Emission Directive (2016), Ecolabel Tourism Decision (2017)
EU mobility policies	The European mobility regulation aims to facilitate the circulation of goods, services and people between Member States in the Schengen Area.	Direct: visa regulation, international mobility, EU mobility in Schengen Area	Schengen Borders Code (Regulation 201x), Visa Code (Regulation 2009), VIS Regulation (2008)

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EU Digital market and Services policies	<p>The EU is promoting a single digital and services market within the European union to facilitate the development of an european digital and service-based economy</p>	<p>Development of the digital platforms offering tourism services, travels and (shared) accomodations (AirBnB, Uber, etc)</p>	<p>Digital Single Market Strategy (2015), Services in the Internal Market Directive (2006)</p>
EU tourism policies <i>Source: eco-union</i>	<p>The European tourism policy aims to create a favorable environment for the development of tourism through: competitiveness, sustainability, and access to financing</p>	<p>Direct: actions to encourage employment, competitiveness, quality and sustainability in the tourism industry</p>	<p>Blue economy communication (2014), Coastal and Maritime tourism communication (2014), Political framework for tourism communication (2010), European Package Travel Directive (2015)</p>
International Marine policies	<p>International legislations on maritime issues are transposed into EU law that can affect tourism through the cruising and nautical tourism industry and their operations.</p>	<p>Indirect: control and regulation over ship discharges, training and employment in the shipping and cruising industry</p>	<p>MARPOL, SOLAS, STCW, UNCLOS III, Regulations on Port State Control inspections</p>

The EU also provides economic schemes to support SMEs across the Union, including in the tourism sector²⁹. To respond to the pandemic crisis, it has also launched initiatives aiming at mainstreaming the use of vouchers for travellers instead of reimbursements for cancelled travels, accomodations and events, in order to support businesses from suffering from cancellations³⁰. Finally the EU is financing a number of regional projects in the field of sustainability through the Interreg funds³¹.

²⁹ EC: [Support to tourism businesses](#). ³⁰ European Parliament (2020): [COVID-19 and the tourism sector](#). ³¹ Interreg MED Sustainable Tourism.

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2.5 A fragmented network of actors and stakeholders

The Mediterranean region is a key economic and political hotspot in Europe and Africa; consequently, it concentrates a large number of stakeholders exploiting markets, building

cooperation and influencing policies at the regional, national and local level.

KEY REGIONAL ACTORS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN TOURISM

KEY ACTORS	MAIN ISSUES	ROLE ON (COASTAL & MARITIME) TOURISM	FLAGSHIP PROJECTS ON (C&M) TOURISM
Public Actors			
European Commission (EC)	Employment, economy, environment, security, research, cooperation	Directives on MSP and MSFD, Blue growth strategy, Interreg fundings	EU ecolabels, Westmed initiative, ETIS, Copernicus, European atlas of the sea
Dividing tourism in Medes islands (Catalonia)	Environmental conservation and protection of European natural ecosystems	Monitoring of the environmental impacts of the tourism industry, environmental policymaking and assessment, as well as citizen participation	Marine Litter Watch, Tourism and the environment report
Union for the Mediterranean (UfM)	International cooperation, environment, energy, inclusion, transport, business	Improvement of cooperation and regional dialogue to protect the Mediterranean Sea; Implementation of project and, regional platform on blue Economy	Med Coasts for Blue Growth (MedCoast4BG), MedECC, WestMed
African Union (AU)	Regional political and development cooperation, Infrastructure and energy, economic affairs, legal affairs, civil society and diaspora	Implementation of the Agenda 2063: Infrastructure for economic integration, including tourism, knowledge on marine and aquatic biodiversity, resource management and protection of ecosystems.	Committee on Transport, Communications and Tourism.
Arab League	Cooperation in social, legal, parliamentary, financial, economic and cultural affairs and conflict resolution	Arab strategy on health and the environment. Facilitate Investments in tourism sectors such as hotels and resorts and other infrastructures.	.
Arab Maghreb Union	Free trade, economic growth, industrial, agricultural, commercial and social development	Maghrebin charter for the protection of the environment and sustainable development (1992). Cooperation convention on the protection of coastal and maritime areas (1991).	Promote Blue tourism and ecotourism through workshops and summits.
UNEP/MAP	Coordination, development, implementation, follow-up and monitoring of the Barcelona Convention	ICZM Protocol, Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development (MSSD) and Sustainable Consumption and Production (sCP) Mediterranean Action Plan	SUPREME and SIMWESTMED; Marine litter; SwitchMed initiative
Plan Bleu/RAC	Regional Activity Centre of UNEP/MAP - Observatory on environment and sustainable development	Programs of activities focusing on sustainable tourism in the Mediterranean. State of Mediterranean Environment and Development - Forecasting report.	

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PAP/RAC	Regional Activity Centre of UNEP/MAP responsible for the coastal management	Promotion of the ICZM framework for sustainable tourism planning	CO-EVOLVE project, ICZM
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Business Associations - Private Actors

Med Cruise	Association of the Mediterranean cruise ports	Common policies and regulations relating to cruise ports	The Sustainable Cruise project (LIFE+)
European Boating Industry	European leisure marine industry	Monitoring of EU legislations, initiatives and actions; lobbying actions with members' support; pressures in favor of policies conducive to navigation at national level in the EU sphere	PHAROS4MPAs, Blue Generation
European Sea Ports Organisation (ESPO)	Association of European Sea Ports	Influence European public policy in favor of the port and maritime sectors	ESPO Environmental report
HOTREC	European hospitality sector (Hotels, Restaurants, Bars and Cafes)	Influence European policies regarding the hospitality sector	Charter on energy efficiency (2018); guidelines on food waste reduction (2017); Charter for environmentally sustainable tourism (2003)
European Tourism Association (ETOA)	Trade association of tour operators and tourism suppliers in European destinations	Political support and lobbying on European policies regarding the tour operators and tourism suppliers in European destinations.	
Cruise Line International Association (CLIA)	World's largest cruise industry trade association	Political advocacy and lobbying related to the cruise, marine, port, tourism and travel policies in Europe and the Mediterranean countries.	
European Regions Airlines Association (ERA)	European aviation industry	Political support and lobbying on European policies regarding air transport (connectivity and airport facilities)	

International NGOs

WWF-Med	Environmental protection Foundation	Actions towards sustainable tourism and public/private partnerships and supported the finalization of MPA tourism management plans	Medtrends
IUCN-Med	Sustainability, conservation and cooperation NGO	Action for Sustainable tourism in Protected Areas	Projects DestiMED; PLASTIMED; MEET association

Source: own elaboration (based on information available on corporate websites)

3 Impacts, benefits and vulnerability of Coastal and Maritime Tourism

Coastal and maritime tourism have significant and growing negative environmental externalities, mainly due to the mass pollution from travel, production and consumption patterns. As this type of tourism is linked to the well-being of natural ecosystems, which provide much of the attractiveness of the region, the Mediterranean needs to invest in environmental protection measures to mitigate these impacts and guarantee its long-term socio-economic sustainability.

3.1 Coastal and maritime tourism activities

Coastal tourism refers to beach-based tourism and recreation activities, including **swimming, sunbathing and surfing**, alongside with other activities taking place on the coast and for which the proximity of the sea is advantageous, such as **coastal walks or wildlife watching**³².

Maritime tourism refers to predominantly water-based activities, such as sailing, yachting and cruising, and other nautical sports. Both

coastal and maritime tourism are among the oldest and largest segments of the tourism industry. They evolved from leisure activities reserved to the wealthiest in the 19th century to more 'democratic' activities within the reach of middle and working classes, especially with the mainstreaming of paid vacations and all-inclusive resorts, and that of affordable means of transportation.

3.2 Environmental impacts of coastal and maritime tourism

The negative environmental impacts of tourism on the coastal and maritime areas of the Mediterranean originate mainly from the **construction and operation of infrastructures** (hotels, second-home residencies, ports and marinas, waste treatment facilities, etc.) and from **maritime or coastal recreational activities** (nautical tourism, golf courses, water sports, etc.). These negative externalities mostly consist of water and energy consumption for tourism services (e.g. swimming pools, golf courses, accommodation, air conditioning)³⁴, especially in water sensitive areas³⁵, where they can also lead to land change, artificialization of the coast, pollution, and biodiversity loss.

Marine litter is also a critical issue: in some Mediterranean tourism areas, more than 75% of the annual waste production is generated during the summer³⁶. It has long been demonstrated that **beach litter** is directly correlated to the number of tourists³⁷. In fact, coastal tourism denigrates ecosystems through multiple pressures, such as waste, water and air pollution, light and noise pollution, alien species, urbanisation, transportation, and resource use. Such pressures do not solely impact the ecosystems within the proximities to the sources

of pressures but impact far away ecosystems, for instance by marine plastic litter, and air pollution from maritime transport, which rapidly disperse with the marine and air currents respectively.

Cruise tourism has strong environmental impacts. Cruise ships travel from port to port highly polluting the air, impacting public health and ecosystems. In fact, the main Mediterranean cruise company, consisting of 47 cruise ships, emits about 10 times more Sulfur oxide (SO_x) than the over 260+ million passenger vehicles in Europe.³⁸ Equally importantly, is the introduction of **alien species** through ballast water of cruise ships, which can potentially result in irreversible damages for the entire ecosystem of the Mediterranean Sea. Cruise ships travel relatively close to the coastline where biodiversity is most vulnerable to pollution.³⁹ Hence, cruise tourism, along with shipping, contribute to the decline of marine species, such as marine mammals affected by ship strike. **Noise pollution**, from cruises and recreational boating, is another major factor which impairs the livelihood of marine fish and mammals along coastal waters, further impoverishing the marine ecosystem⁴⁰.

³² Ecorys (2013): *Study in support of policy measures for maritime and coastal tourism at EU level*. ³³ Honey M. & Krantz D. (2007): *Global Trends in Coastal Tourism*. ³⁴ Gössling, S. (2002): *Global environmental consequences of tourism*; EEA - UNEP/MAP (2014): *Horizon 2020 mediterranean report*; EP (2017) *Briefing European Parliamentary Research Service*; EEA (2017): *Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2016*. ³⁵ Plan Bleu (2010): *Management of energy air transport and tourism in the Mediterranean*. ³⁶ Giulietti and al. (2018): *Tourism and the environment Towards a reporting mechanism in Europe*. EEA Report (ETC/ULS). ³⁷ Grelaud, M., Ziveri, P. (2020): *The generation of marine litter in Mediterranean island beaches as an effect of tourism and its mitigation*. *Sci Rep.* ³⁸ Abassov, F. and al. (2019): *One corporation to pollute them all*. *Transport & Environment*. ³⁹ *Transport & Environment: Cruise ships*. ⁴⁰ Plan Bleu (2020): *State of the Mediterranean marine and coastal environment*.

3 Impacts, benefits and vulnerability of Coastal and Maritime Tourism

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF COASTAL TOURISM ACTIVITIES

THREATS FROM CT	CT TYPOLOGIES				
	Boating				
Airpollution	●	●	●	●	●
Solid waste	●	●	●	●	●
Ecosystem Degradation	●	●	●	●	●
Water pollution	●	●	●	●	●
Noise pollution	●	●	●	●	●
Light pollution	●	●	●	●	●
Wildlife disturbance	●	●	●	●	●
Alien species	●	●	●	●	●
Resource use	●	●	●	●	●

Source: *CO-EVOLVE*, based on literature review. The level of threat is ranked from low (light), medium or high (dark).

Given the anticipated sectoral growth⁴¹, these environmental and social pressures are likely to increase if adequate regulation of tourism flows is not implemented. As Northern Mediterranean countries are a rather mature tourism destination, these pressures are likely to increase in the coming years in Southern Mediterranean Countries.

⁴¹ UNWTO.

3.3 Dependency of tourism on natural ecosystems

The tourism industry is composed of and interacts with many **different economic sectors**, including transport, agriculture, construction or foods & drinks. It also depends on several

functional services usually provided by local authorities, such as water, energy supply, waste or sewage management.

ECOSYSTEM SERVICES RELATED TO TOURISM SECTOR

Source: European Environment Agency, 2015⁴²

Coastal and Maritime tourism is therefore highly dependent on the quality of natural ecosystems. With 46,000km of coastline and unique marine and fisheries resources, the Mediterranean Sea represents the fifth largest economy in the region, with an overall value estimated at **US\$5.6 trillion** (4.7 trillion euros)⁴³. It estimates that ocean-related activities in the Mediterranean sea generate an annual economic value of \$450 billion, representing about **20% of the annual global GDP**, with **tourism accounting for 92%** of the Mediterranean's economic production.

The environmental pressures from human induced activities are taking a toll on the tourist industry as it lowers **the attractiveness of**

tourist destinations⁴⁴. This loss of attractiveness due to pressures from coastal tourism is evident from waste pollution, including presence of faecal water in beaches, and degradation of flora and fauna due to water scarcity derived from tourist infrastructure. The development of coastal tourism infrastructure, which is especially dense from Southern Spain to Northern Italy, has eliminated entire ecosystems and has resulted in highly vulnerable economies dependent on mass tourism⁴⁵. Infrastructure leads to light pollution which exacerbates the survival of coastal species as it alters their reproductive cycles and confuses species, such as new-born turtles which race inland towards artificial light instead of to the sea⁴⁶.

⁴² EEA (2015): *European ecosystem assessment. Technical Report 6/2015*. ⁴³ Randone and al. (2017): *Reviving the Economy of the Mediterranean Sea: Actions for a Sustainable future*, WWF Mediterranean Marine Initiative. ⁴⁴ Drius et al. (2019): *Tackling challenges for Mediterranean sustainable coastal tourism: An ecosystem service perspective*, Science of The Total Environment. ⁴⁵ Greenpeace (2018): *A Toda Costa*. ⁴⁶ Elizabeth Howell (2013): *Light Pollution Deters Nesting Sea Turtles*, LiveScience.

3 Impacts, benefits and vulnerability of Coastal and Maritime Tourism

ENVIRONMENTAL THREATS TO COASTAL TOURISM ACTIVITIES

THREATS FROM CT	CT TYPOLOGIES				
	Boating				
Airpollution	●	●	●	●	●
Solid waste	●	●	●	●	●
Ecosystem Degradation	●	●	●	●	●
Water pollution	●	●	●	●	●
Noise pollution	●	●	●	●	●
Light pollution	●	●	●	●	●
Wildlife disturbance	●	●	●	●	●
Alien species	●	●	●	●	●
Resource use	●	●	●	●	●

Source: *CO-EVOLVE*, based on literature review. The level of threat is ranked from low (light), medium or high (dark).

All of these impacts have **negative feedback** to the tourist industry as they result in destinations losing attractiveness due to the increased health risk, lingering resources, impoverished ecosystems, and loss of local people. Furthermore, coastal tourism requires aeroplanes, trains, buses, and private vehicles

that lead to high GHG emissions, contributing to extreme weather events, ocean acidification, sea-level rise and other climate change-related processes, which are the most crucial factors endangering touristic destinations.

3.4 Tourism vulnerability to climate change

The Mediterranean tourism sector is exposed to growing pressures linked to the effects of climate change. Coastal erosion, for example, is already evident throughout the Mediterranean coast, especially in the southern part. Lack of water, coastal erosion, rising sea levels are just some of the challenges that climate change poses to tourism operators and other stakeholders on the shores of the Mediterranean Sea. Although some impacts are still limited, future forecasts will increase rapidly.

The most worrying impact of climate change on tourism sector in the medium (2030) and

long-term (2050) are in the Eastern (Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon and Palestine) and Western (Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia) southern countries⁴⁷:

- **Direct impacts:** loss of visits and increase in direct costs due to high climate instability that discourages local visitors and in particular international visitors.
- **Indirect impacts:** decrease of attractiveness due to the local biodiversity losses characterizing the destination, as well as the deterioration of local essential infrastructures (transport, hospitality, etc.) due to flood pressure.

⁴⁷ UfM (2018): *Climate change impact on the tourism sector in the southern Mediterranean*.

3 Impacts, benefits and vulnerability of Coastal and Maritime Tourism

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE TOURISM SECTOR IN THE SOUTHERN MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES

J=Jordan, I=Israel, L=Lebanon, P=Palestine, E=Egypt, T=Tunisia, A=Algeria, M=Morocco

Source: UfM (2018)⁴⁸

Some important direct impacts on the tourism sector are not immediately visible. This causes a distortion of the climate change risk perception of the tourism sector operators, which, to date, have not given priority to adaptation and mitigation actions to climate change, increasing the vulnerability of destinations in the Mediterranean coast.

⁴⁸ UfM (2018): *Climate change impact on the tourism sector in the southern Mediterranean*.

4 Environmental management of coastal and marine tourism

This chapter assesses benefits from management frameworks for sustainable coastal and marine tourism as well as reviews essential policy tools that can facilitate the effective implementation and monitoring of management plans for sustainable tourism.

4 Environmental management of coastal and marine tourism

4.1 Coastal, marine and land planning

Planning the use of **marine space** is still an underdeveloped task, which will require more effort to reach a similar level of maturity reached by planning of terrestrial surfaces. The following

table compares the benefits of different management frameworks that can be used for the development of sustainable Coastal and Marine Tourism (CMT).

MARINE, COASTAL AND LAND-USE PLANNING

FRAMEWORK	APPROACH	BENEFITS	CHALLENGES
Public Actors			
Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) ⁴⁹	Planification of human activities in marine areas through ecosystem-based, integrated, adaptive, strategic and participatory processes. ⁵⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Achieves Good Environmental Status (GES) - Improves climate resilience - Prevents overflow of tourism - Distributes environmental pressures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication - Engagement of all stakeholders⁵¹.
Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) ⁵²	Integration of terrestrial and marine environments taking into account ecosystems, landscapes, human activities and their interactions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid conflicts between coastal users - Adds value to product with eco-labelling - Ameliorates environmental status - Encourages participation - Prevents overflow of tourism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and predictability - Costs - Low engagement of private sector - Difficult to implement
Land-use planning	Intends to manage land (including coastal zones) to optimise the social, environmental and economic outcomes through the practice of zoning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Targets economic, social, and ecological objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not specific to the marine environment - Focused on coastal land

Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) and land-use planning both manage the activities within a space through the designation of respective zones. However, while MSP may disregard further in-land zones, land-use planning, in turn, often ignores marine zones. Therefore, as land and marine processes interact with each other, for instance, marine eutrophication due to runoff agriculture nutrients, MSP and land-use planning

should be integrated. On the other hand, ICZM is similar to MSP in that it also addresses inadequate governance in marine settings through participative solutions. Nevertheless, ICZM does not systematically implement zoning for specific maritime activities. Hence, MSP and ICZM can work alongside in addressing both environmental and economic issues in a destination⁵³.

⁴⁹ World Ocean Council (2016): *Marine Spatial Planning: Case Studies*. ⁵⁰ Papageorgiou, M. (2016): *Coastal and marine tourism: A challenging factor in Marine Spatial Planning*. *Ocean & Coastal Management*. ⁵¹ WOC (2016): *Marine Spatial Planning: Case Studies*. ⁵² UNEP (2009): *Sustainable Coastal Tourism: an integrated planning and management approach*. ⁵³ Jay, S. (2017): *Marine Spatial Planning Assessing net benefits and improving effectiveness*. OECD.

4 Environmental management of coastal and marine tourism

4.2 Policy tools for sustainable tourism

Policy tools are essential to ensure long-standing sustainable management of tourism. Though, their success in achieving sustainable tourism will greatly depend on the political will of the relevant authorities, access to finance, engagement of all stakeholders, as well as

the availability and quality of data required to develop sound long-term management strategies. The following table illustrates different policy tools that national and local governments can use to facilitate sustainable tourism.

POLICY TOOLS SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

TOOL	DESCRIPTION	CHALLENGES
Green taxes	Green taxes are directed to penalize practices that are harmful to the environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing amounts that effectively incentivise green practices - Managing pressure from affected stakeholders
Tourist tax	Levies on tourist establishments to restore negative impacts of the tourism activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Managing pressure from affected stakeholders (e.g. Catalan and Balearic cases⁵⁴)
Carrying capacity	Establishing a physical limit to tourist activities and number of visitors to ensure long-term environmental/social sustainability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing sciences-based limits - Managing pressure from affected stakeholders - Difficult to implement in urban areas - Difficult to measure
Ecological footprint	Indicator that measures the biologically productive requirements to assimilate the consumption and waste produced in a destination by tourism activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty in accounting all factors - Does not identify location of specific impacts
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Integrated indicator measuring the environmental impact of each component of tourism (such as accommodation, transport, food...)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty in accounting all factors. - Lack of data accessibility and quality.
Sustainable tourism indicators	Broad set of indicators developed by public or private bodies for measuring the state of sustainable tourism in a destination ⁵⁵ .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific needs of each destination - Lack of data quality, accessibility or transparency - Low stakeholder involvement

In the table above, green and tourist taxes differentiate from the other tools in the sense that they do not directly offer relevant data of the sustainability of tourism in a destination. Green taxes reduce unsustainable practices of tourism while a general tourist tax only contributes to sustainable tourism if the revenues collected are invested in the sustainability of the destination. On the other hand, carrying capacity, ecological

footprint, lifecycle assessments, and sustainable tourism indicators are all indicators that are essential—though not sufficient—for the effective planning of sustainable tourism in a destination.

⁵⁴ Wibo Sefeld (2016) *Tourist Taxes: Review and Enforcement*. ⁵⁵ See for eg : UNWTO (2016): *Measuring Sustainable Tourism: Developing a statistical framework for sustainable tourism*; EC (2016): *The European Tourism Indicator System: ETIS toolkit for sustainable destination management*.

4.3 Eco-labelling tourism schemes

Eco-label is a label based on specific criteria, usually determined through a participatory and regularly updated process⁵⁶. These criteria are used to assess the manufacture and transformation of a product, the offer of services or the design of a management system. The compliance with these criteria is verified by an inspection body, which is supposed to be independent. In most cases, the criteria of a label are specifically determined for a group of products or a service sector such as eco-tourism

labels. Some labels are official ones, awarded by the Member States (e.g. EU ecolabel), or awarded by an organisation (e.g. Travelife), or by a company (e.g. Green Globe). Eco-label is a voluntary process and labels need to comply with the national legislation. However, ecolabels vary in terms of credibility and transparency given that there is a wide variety of specifications and working methods among certifying bodies.

ECO-LABELS FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

NAME	TYPE OF ORGANIZATION	SECTOR	OBJECTIVE
BIO Hotels	Industry association (Austria)	Organic and regional products in Hotels (Germany)	Environmental sustainability and CO2 emissions reduction.
Biosphere Tourism	Non-profit (Spain)	Destinations and tourist routes; Accommodations; Tourists cities and centers; Parks; Tour operators	Promote sustainable development actions and programs in tourism destinations and companies.
Blue Flag	Non-profit (Netherlands)	Beaches and marinas	Environmental quality and sustainability of coastal areas.
Blue Angel	Governmental (Germany)	Tourism and other	Protection goals: health, climate, water, and resources.
Earth Check	Private-oriented (Australia)	Tourism	Scientific benchmarking certification and advisory for travel and tourism.
Ecolabel	Governmental (EU & France)	Tourism and other	Encourage businesses to market greener products and services and allow consumers to identify them.
Green Seal	Non-profit (USA)	Tourism and other	Life-cycle approach to ensure tangible reductions in the whole environmental footprint.
Green Key	Non-profit (Denmark)	Tourism businesses	Environmental Sustainability.
Rainforest Alliance	Non-profit (USA & Netherlands)	Tourism and other sectors	Alliance of farmers, forest communities, companies, and consumers committed to creating a world where people and nature thrive in harmony.

Source: own elaboration based on Ecolabel Index⁵⁷

⁵⁶ Switch Med (2017): Sustainable tourism labels. ⁵⁷ Ecolabels Index: EcoLabels on tourism.

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

The tourism industry was in full expansion in the Mediterranean region when the 2020 pandemic of COVID-19 shut down travellers globally, bringing about disastrous consequences for the economy of Mediterranean countries and for the tourism industry in particular. While a return to normalcy may take time, national recovery plans are being implemented to overcome the crisis's economic and social impacts. Additionally, some initiatives are emerging on both sides of the Mediterranean region to rebuild the industry into a more sustainable and fair one.

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

5.1 Global Impact of the COVID-19 crisis

The tourism sector has been dramatically affected in 2020 as countries worldwide followed confinements and mobility restrictions to stop the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic⁵⁸. The decline in economic activity and travel worldwide started in the second half of March 2020. As of June, 2020, the fall of international arrivals

amounted to 93% compared to what it was at the same date the year before. Air travel, but also maritime and train travel, saw a drastic decline in activity. At the same time, cruise ships stood stranded at sea as ports and frontiers closed down to stop the spread of the disease.

TYPE OF TRAVEL RESTRICTION BY COUNTRIES (APRIL 2020)

- Complete or partial closing of borders
- Suspension of flights
- Destination-specific travel restriction
- Different measures

Source: Data compiled by UNWTO as of 27 April 2020

Global tourism suffered its worst year on record in 2020, with international arrivals dropping by 74% according to the latest data from the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Destinations worldwide received 1 billion fewer international arrivals in 2020 than in the previous year, due to an unprecedented fall in demand and widespread travel restrictions. This compares with the 4% decline recorded during the 2009 global economic crisis. The collapse of international travel represents an estimated loss of USD 1.3 trillion in export revenues - more than 11 times the loss recorded during the 2009 global

economic crisis. The crisis has put between 100 and 120 million direct tourism jobs at risk, many of them in small and medium-sized enterprises⁵⁹.

⁵⁸ UNWTO (2020); *International Tourism and covid-19*. ⁵⁹ UNWTO (2021); 2020: WORST YEAR IN TOURISM HISTORY WITH 1 BILLION FEWER INTERNATIONAL ARRIVALS.

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

YEAR TO YEAR CHANGE IN INTERNATIONAL TOURIST ARRIVALS PER REGIONS (2020 VS 2019)

Change (%) 2020, by region

Source: UNWTO

Asia and the Pacific (-84% ITAs) - the first region to suffer from the impact of the pandemic and the one with the highest level of travel restrictions currently in place - recorded the largest decrease in arrivals in 2020 (300 million fewer). The Middle East and Africa both recorded a 75% decline. Europe recorded a 70% decrease

in arrivals, despite a small and short-lived revival in the summer of 2020. The region suffered the largest drop in absolute terms, with over 500 million fewer international tourists in 2020. The Americas saw a 69% decrease in international arrivals, following somewhat better results in the last quarter of the year.

INTERNATIONAL TOURIST ARRIVALS (ITA) IN EUROPEAN SOUTHERN MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES (2019-2020)

Thousands

● Current year (2020)
● Previous year (2019)
Source: UNWTO

The immobilisation of global tourism has severely impacted the **labour tourism market**. Tourism is highly gender segregated and women tend to occupy job roles that have

been the most affected by social distancing and restrictive measures. Women account for 61% of workers in tourism, retail, hospitality, and aviation⁶⁰. The vulnerability of women could be

60 Eurofound (2020): *Women and labour market equality: Has COVID-19 rolled back recent gains?*

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

worse in the case of low-income immigrants. Therefore, due to the precarious nature of the tourism market (temporal contracts and low salaries), the structural gender inequality, and the instability and uncertainty produced by the Covid19 pandemic, could have led to worst labour conditions. Similarly, due to the closure of many small businesses in hospitality and tourism, many workers, entrepreneurs and self-employed, were left without work. Therefore, the crisis could

lead to increased gender inequality, and the risk of poverty and exclusion of many precarity workers. Situations are likely to differ depending on the different welfare states regimes of the Mediterranean region, among those with better and worse social protection, as many low income workers are highly dependent on economic transfers from states.

5.2 The mediterranean economy disrupted by the global lock-downs

Despite being the world's most visited destination, European 2020 touristic season saw 213 million less international arrivals than in 2019. The subregion of Southern Mediterranean Europe had the second largest decline in tourist arrivals after North-East Asia, with a record 72% decline compared to 2019 numbers. In the European continent, Italy, Spain and France, accounting for half of the sectors, were the hardest-hit from the pandemic.

The organization of cultural, commercial and sports mass events across the globe has been shaken for fear of spreading the virus. While major events like the Summer Olympic Games in Japan or the Cannes Film Festival in France have been postponed to a later date, others, like

the national Marathons, music festivals or the Holy Week in Spain and Italy, have been outright cancelled, leading to losses of revenues for venues, hotels and restaurants. The events that have turned fully digital similarly translate into gigantic economic losses. In the Mediterranean region, the Mobile World 2020 Congress that was to take place in Barcelona, Spain, as well as the IUCN World Conservation Congress planned in Marseille, France were postponed. During the summer, some countries across the Mediterranean region saw a rebound of visitors, while still enduring health restrictions. Intra-Regional travel increased, with tourists preferring to travel within their countries of origin and avoiding air travel.

INTERNATIONAL TOURIST ARRIVALS (ITA) IN EUROPEAN SOUTHERN MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES (2019-20)

Thousands

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In the Northern Mediterranean, **Spain**⁶¹ is the country which suffered the most from the COVID-19 outbreak. The government adopted measures such as tax deferrals and exemptions, and protected the workers affected by the crisis through temporary employment adjustment schemes. In **France**, the lockdown measures heavily impacted the tourism sector, which then suffered a slowed-down summer season. Measures enforced by the government to remedy the situation include a credit facilitation instead of refunds for the hotels and accommodations suffering cancelled bookings, as well as 18€ billion to support the various actors of the tourism sector. In **Greece**, the loss due to the pandemic for the year 2020 amounted to an estimated 522€ million in terms of cancellations only, with about 20% of the hotel employment at risk. However, Greece had a summer season less dramatic than neighboring countries due to its early control of the outbreak. The government set up a Crisis Management Committee for the Coronavirus, which provided information to

Tourism operators and proposed a package of measures for recovery.

For the Southern Mediterranean, in **Morocco**⁶², the government also contributed to protecting unemployed people and deferred social contribution payments for a number of sectors, including tourism. In addition, the Tourism ministry launched a label guaranteeing the respect of health safety protocols in tourism accommodation establishments, "Welcome Safely", in order to restore customer's confidence in the destination. In Tunisia, where international travel hit a 80% decline in the first semester of 2020 compared to the year prior, a policy of deferral of payments for the operators of the tourism sector suffering from the pandemic was enabled.

5.3 An uncertain future: Back to normal or a full reset?

As by end of January 2021, more than **100 million COVID-19 cases** have been confirmed worldwide⁶³, according to the World Health Organization. The social and economic consequences for the tourism sector will thus be felt for years to come, and the uncertainty is still a major factor in the equation, forbidding both public and private actors to build up hope for a quick recovery. While in the second half of 2020, 53% of destinations temporarily eased travel restrictions⁶⁴, it will be a slow recovery. The **seniors**, for example, could be fearful of travelling for the upcoming years, while those subject to financial setbacks brought about by the COVID 19-induced economic crisis will have less disposable income to spend in tourism.

The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) drew **scenarios** of what the sector can

expect in the coming months, based on various estimates of the COVID-19 spread. However, the return to the pre-pandemic level of 2019 is not expected before **3 to 4 years**, depending on the vaccine timeline. These scenarios point to a rebound in the year 2021, provided that the contagion numbers decrease, which would lead to a boost in travelers confidence on the side of the customers and a lifting of travel restrictions on the side of government regulations. The first scenario draws a recovery for mid 2023, the second by the end of 2023 and the third by the end of 2024. For 2021 at least, the numbers of international arrivals will remain below those of 2019 in all cases⁶⁵.

⁶¹ OECD (2020) : *Tourism Policy Responses to COVID-19*. ⁶² IMF (2020): *Policy Responses to COVID-19*. ⁶³ Johns Hopkins University (2020): *Coronavirus Resource Center*. ⁶⁴ UNWTO (2020): *More than 50% of Global Destinations are Easing Travel Restrictions*. ⁶⁵ UNWTO (2020) *International Tourism and covid-19*.

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

2021-24 SCENARIOS TO RECOVER INTERNATIONAL TOURIST ARRIVALS

2 1/2 TO 4 YEARS TO RECOVER 2019 LEVELS

Millions

The only steady trend in the foreseeable future is the resuming of **domestic tourism** within European countries. Due to travel restrictions, closed borders and the risks of transmission via air travel, intraregional and domestic tourism are privileged by travelers⁶⁶. Indeed, The OECD forecast for 2020⁶⁷ shows that domestic tourism is the backbone of the Tourism industry, with 75% of tourism expenditure coming from internal travelers. Domestic tourism is what will drive the recovery for the industry⁶⁸. Domestic tourism also suffered the least dramatic drop compared to international arrivals: in Europe, in July 2020, there was only a 22% decline compared to 2019 in nights spent by EU residents in tourist

accommodation inside their own country - compared to a 64% for non-national tourists⁶⁹. Many countries have thus started offering **incentives to national travelers**, from renewed marketing campaigns to subsidies to facilities so that they are more affordable for low to middle-class vacationers. Such examples include: In Italy, a *"Bonus Vacanze"* contributing up to 500€ to families with low-middle incomes to spend in domestic tourism locations; or a nationwide campaign highlighting the country's destinations in France.

5.4 The decarbonisation of travel and tourism

Obviously, the tourism sector as it stood pre-pandemic was highly unsustainable. Transport, including international travels, was the biggest emitting sector across the European Union, ranging between 15 to 40% of countries' carbon emissions, with total transport emissions accounting for about 30% of all EU emissions.

Maritime transportation represents nearly 4% of this number⁷⁰. At a global scale, carbon emissions from tourism are estimated roughly at 8% of total carbon emissions, mainly due to air transport, growing year after year⁷¹.

⁶⁶ UNWTO (2020): *Market Intelligence*. ⁶⁷ OECD (2020): *Tourism Trends and Policies*. ⁶⁸ UNWTO (2020): *Highlights Potential of Domestic Tourism to Help Drive Economic Recovery in Destinations Worldwide*. ⁶⁹ European Commission (2020): *Domestic tourism recovers faster than foreign tourism - Product*. ⁷⁰ European Environmental Agency (2018): *Transport emissions of greenhouse-gases*. ⁷¹ Lenzen, M., Sun, YY., Faturay, F. and al. (2018): *The carbon footprint of global tourism*. *Nature Climate Change*.

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

CARBON FOOTPRINT OF GLOBAL TOURISM

The initial impact of the pandemic on global climate looks positive, but it is only temporary. The worldwide lockdown measures have led to less demand in transportation, electricity and industry, and a 8% reduction in global CO₂ emissions is expected for 2020, the most important since the Second World War⁷².

However, the recovery curb is expected to take a bigger toll on climate than ever before, and countries are expected to have to choose between the economy and the climate measures needed to keep global warming below 1,5°.

5.5 Digitalization and alternative tourism models

Two major trends are increasingly impacting the tourism sector: **Digitalization** and the emergence of **alternative tourism models**. Destinations, tour operators and travel agencies, on their part, are starting to reduce the dependency on over-crowded locations and promote environmentally friendly journeys, in order to manage travel flows and generate value in less-travelled areas. They should engage local communities and SMES in the planning process, develop sustainable products focused on biodiversity or culture⁷³. The tools of storytelling permitted by the progresses of digitalization allows for personalized, valuable experiences

that shun mass tourism and favor the protection of the environment travelled to. Contactless technologies, biometrics and Artificial Intelligence are all part of this trend. In addition, **digitalization**, as well as reskilling and up-skilling tourism workers will destroy but should also create jobs. Investing in the human capital locally is the best way to sustain a balance between quality tourism and biodiversity protection. It must be guaranteed that no workers or communities are left behind in the **tourism transition**. To remedy that, public authorities should invest in digital competences. Digitalization has the power to better inform

⁷² IEA (2020) : Global energy and CO₂ emissions in 2020 – Global Energy Review 2020 – Analysis. ⁷³ Interreg MED Sustainable Tourism.

5 The COVID-19 Pandemic Impact on the Mediterranean Tourism

decision-making by making realtime information and best practices widely available: notably, the compliance of enterprises to environmental and social sustainability.

In **Italy**, during the lockdown, there has been virtual tours and cooking classes by famous chefs, at a time where the real-life experience was impossible⁷⁴. Museums and heritage sites all around the world have held virtual exhibitions. At the European Union level, the online platform Europeana⁷⁵ has been launched to present to the public cultural artifacts. In the second quarter of 2020, the application **Cultural Gems**⁷⁶ has launched an initiative encouraging proximity tourism. This allows people who, because of physical or financial access, could not enjoy these cultural exhibits in person to do so. However, this digitalization of touristic locations and happenings may deepen inequality for remote

places that are unconnected, and the ecological impact of entire museums going online, for example, is still unclear.

The integration of **Social and Solidarity Economy** (SSE) in the blue economy sectors such as coastal and maritime tourism is a clear framework to align socio-economic benefits and environmental protection, increasing local communities' resilience and ensuring long term sustainability⁷⁷. Tour operators and travel agencies should, on their side, reduce the carbon and water footprint of their supply chain, avoid food waste, eliminate single-use plastics, prioritize low-carbon transports, partner with local providers, provide appropriate training and salaries to their working force.

⁷⁴ Università degli Studi di Bergamo (2020) : Tourism facing a pandemic: from crisis to recovery. ⁷⁵ European Commission (2020): EU Tourism and COVID-19 pandemic: an EU response to exit and recovery. ⁷⁶ <https://culturalgems.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>. ⁷⁷ eco-union (2020) : Towards a Blue Solidarity Economy.

6 A Green and Inclusive Recovery Plan for the Mediterranean Tourism

6.1 The recovery funds, a massive Investment in the economy

The European Commission was already on track to establish a **Green New Deal** path for the European Union before the coronavirus pandemic. The emission reduction target was established at 40% by 2030. The recovery and stimulus measures will be implemented under this framework, which includes about €225 billion (US\$190 billion) in recovery funds and €322 billion (US\$280 billion) for the 2021–2027 budget, aimed at bringing Member States to achieve climate action goals. In terms of maritime and coastal measures, it remains to be seen what policies will be implemented at the national level. However, the European Commission has already communicated its **Farm to Fork** strategy, which aims at reforming the food system sustainably. It includes clauses on the reduction of the use of fertilisers and pesticides, which are direct causes of marine pollution.

The European Union Commission's Environment Committee has also brought up the topic of an **Ocean Fund**⁷⁸ aimed at making ships more energy efficient and supporting green infrastructures implementation in the maritime sector, to be enacted in the 2023 to 2030 period. The Ocean Fund would be jointly financed by revenues from the auctioning allowances under the carbon Emissions Trading System (ETS) and the European Investment Bank (EIB), who committed to double its lending to sustainable

ocean projects, up to €2.5 billion (\$2.7 billion), over the next five years.

At the Mediterranean level, the **Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development**⁷⁹ (MSSD) integrates sustainable tourism as a strategic objective to be reached by 2025. However, the rather limited mandate of the Barcelona Convention towards environmental issues impedes significant progress on this cross-sectorial issue. A proposal to develop a **Regional sustainable tourism framework** has not been advanced yet⁸⁰, although the tourism sector is included in the **Sustainable Consumption and Production Regional Action Plan** (SCP RAP) to be implemented by Southern Mediterranean country by 2026, with rather limited impact so far⁸¹.

Among other regional initiatives targeting the tourism sector, the European Union (EU) has launched the **WestMed**⁸² initiative to promote a more sustainable blue economy in Western Mediterranean countries. It integrates coastal and marine tourism, sharing Southern and Northern best practices such as the Interreg Med Tourism projects⁸³. The Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) is operating **Blue Economy platform**⁸⁴ and organizing on a regular basis a regional Stakeholders conference to engage policy and decision makers as well as practitioners and researchers.

6.2 Opportunities for sustainable recovery

Although the projects, policies and initiatives mentioned earlier are valuable and contribute, in one way or another, to the sustainable tourism in the Mediterranean, they are in general lacking a structured and robust governance system at regional level that could ensure the necessary social and environmental transformation of the tourism sector. Tourism is a globalized

yet fragmented industry that needs to be monitored, managed and regulated at various space, time and geographic scales⁸⁵.

⁷⁸ EC: *Why the EU supports research and innovation in oceans and seas*. ⁷⁹ UNEP/MAP (2016): *Mediterranean Strategy for Sustainable Development 2016-25*. ⁸⁰ Fosse et Al. (2017): *Towards a blue economy for a sustainable Mediterranean: Indicators and recommendations*. ⁸¹ UNEP/MAP (2016): *Regional Action Plan on Sustainable Production and Consumption in the Mediterranean*. ⁸² *WestMed Blue Economy Initiative*. ⁸³ *Interreg MED Sustainable Tourism*. ⁸⁴ *Mediterranean Blue Economy Stakeholders Platform*. ⁸⁵ Eco-union (2019): *Towards a Sustainable Blue Tourism*.

6 A Green and Inclusive Recovery Plan for the Mediterranean Tourism

CRITERIA TO ENSURE A BLUE STIMULUS RECOVERY

- 1 **Coastal and Marine Ecosystem Restoration and Protection**, such as deltas, salt marshes, sea grasses and coral reefs. Besides providing employment from high-skilled conservationism to small-scale artisanry, these ecosystems make up natural protection from flood damage, filter water and provide carbon sinks
- 2 **Wastewater and Sewerage Infrastructures** to avoid damages in coastal ecosystems and marine animals wellbeing, creating local jobs, preventing water-borne diseases, increasing water security for locals, bettering of water quality for coastal and maritime tourism experiences.
- 3 **Sustainable, Community-led Marine Aquaculture** such as shellfish and seaweed farming. Circular economy practices can both feed the population and reduce greenhouse emissions.
- 4 **Zero-emission Marine Transport** through tax cuts, policy measures (such as Emissions Control Areas) and loans to retrofit vessels and ports.
- 5 **Sustainable Ocean-based Renewable Energy**. Ocean-based renewable energy has a high potential and could help coastal and maritime countries end their use of fossil fuels, while creating jobs.
- 6 **Limited capacity measures** for regions with a biodiversity risk. The number of available visitors or rooms can be reduced, as well as that of day-trips to benefit both the livability for local communities and the toll on natural assets.

Source: *High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy*

The involvement of the private sector, financial actors, academic world and civil society organizations is critical to implement significant change and take advantage of the recovery and resilience plans⁸⁶. All of these measures should be multifold, involving various actors and benefitting in many ways the environmental, social and economic environment, as highlighted by the **High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy**⁸⁷.

⁸⁶ UNWTO (2020) : *International Tourism and covid-19*. ⁸⁷ *High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy*.

POLICIES FOR A SUSTAINABLE AND EQUITABLE POST-COVID MEDITERRANEAN TOURISM

Public authorities

- Support re-skills and upskills of tourism workers in digitalization and sustainable management through training programs targeting youth and women in particular.
- Finance research and innovation programs on environmental and social management through public funding and knowledge sharing activities.
- Involve local Communities, Businesses and Civil Society Organizations in the tourism planning, decision and policy processes as well as Recovery and Resilient Plans.
- Promote ecological and social certifications to indicate to the market and consumers the environmental, social and economic benefits of sustainable tourism.

Insurance and finance sectors

- Invest in ecosystem restoration (blue bonds), which has an important return on investment in terms of natural capital to mitigate climate change impacts such as Sea Level Rise (SLR), coastal erosion or extreme climate events.
- Finance the retrofitting of existing facilities to implement net-zero emissions and energy efficiency systems; requiring switching to self-produced renewable energy (Prosumers).
- Support green infrastructures based on Nature-based Solutions (NbS), with low ecological footprint and high socio-economic benefits.
- Phase out support to carbon intensive infrastructures and facilities such as airport extensions, brown assets and other potentially harmful investments.

Maritime industry

- Retrofit and eco-design vessels, electrify ports, implement fuel and water efficiency systems, build renewable energy facilities to become prosumers.
- Invest in smart monitoring and technology, prioritize multi-modal connections, improve efficiency of logistics and supply chain.
- Support an Emission Control Area (ECA) in the Mediterranean to reduce air and marine pollution from vessels and ships.

Tour operators, hotels and resorts

- Implement circular waste management systems in facilities through low water footprint, reusing grey water, treating black water and recuperating rainwater.
- Develop organic and local food systems, eliminating food waste, investing in organic products, prioritizing local suppliers and responsible value chains.
- Educate and train visitors and staff on the necessary behavioral changes to reduce energy and water use, prioritizing low-carbon transportation such as electric cars, low-carbon public transport and international trains.

7 Conclusion

The coronavirus pandemic provoked a deep recession for the tourism sector, leaving Mediterranean countries and industry actors, large and small, in a dramatic economic situation. Public and international subsidies have attempted to remedy the severe losses of jobs and income, with weak results so far. The road towards recovery is dominated by uncertainty as there is no end in sight to the pandemic. Domestic tourism has a critical role in supporting the local tourism industry, hotels, restaurants and tour operators while expecting the deployment of vaccines that would reduce travel bans, which can take several years.

At the same time, it is crucial that the decision and policy-makers from the public and private sectors play their part in turning the industry into a more sustainable one, ensuring positive externalities for the environment, the workers and the local communities. The massive investments provided by the recovery plans offer a unique opportunity to transform the tourism sector and ensure a better future for the whole Mediterranean region. In particular, the progressive phasing out of the fossil fuel energy in the travel and tourism sector is needed to match the 2050 climate neutrality target. Quickly substituting carbon intensive air travels by electric mobility (cars, buses or trains) is essential, while low-carbon technology is developed for airplanes.

Building robust governance mechanisms to monitor and guide the restarting of tourism at local, national or regional level is also vital to ensure more adequate, proactive and efficient policies and practices in the environmental or social arena. A multi-stakeholders and multi-level approach with the integration of local communities, destinations, industry, NGOs and Academia will guarantee a better contribution of tourism to the achievement of the Agenda 2030, which remains one of the few multilateral environmental and social commitments shared by all Mediterranean countries.

8 For more information

Tourism Recovery Tracker (UNWTO): <https://www.unwto.org/unwto-tourism-recovery-tracker>

Blue Tourism Initiative (eco-union, IDDRI, ADEME): <https://www.ecounion.eu/en/portfolio/blue-tourism/>

Tourism Policies Monitoring (OECD): <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/tourism/>

State of Environment and Development in the Mediterranean (Plan Bleu): <https://planbleu.org/en/soed-2020-state-of-environment-and-development-in-mediterranean/>

9 Examples of Good environmental practices

An aerial photograph of a beach. The top portion of the image shows clear, turquoise water. Below it is a wide, light-colored sandy beach with some darker, rocky patches. At the bottom, white foam from waves is washing onto the shore. The overall scene is a natural coastal environment.

9 Examples of Good environmental practices

9 Examples of Good environmental practices

HOTELS, RESORTS AND TOUR OPERATORS

NAME OF ACTION	LOCATION	DATE	ACTOR DRIVING THE INITIATIVE (NAME OF KEY ACTOR)	SCALE OF ACTION	KEY AREA OF ACTION	DESCRIPTION (OUTCOME)
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Accommodation structures

Gîtes Panda	France	Since 1993	ONG-Industry partnership (WWF + Gîtes de France)	National (FR)	Energy, eco-habitat, awareness,	Partnership for eco-construction and eco-renovation, campaigns of awareness for clients. [Mitigation prevention]
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Labels and certifications

Global Ecosphere Retreat Standard	All	2015	NGO (The Long Run)	Global	Ecosystems and biodiversity Local community and culture, fair trade	Labelling and promoting sustainable destinations via strict technical specifications. [Prevention, mitigation]
Ecolabel Toolbox	France	2015	European Union, ADEME, EU Ecolabel, ShMILE	National (FR)	Energy, water, waste...	Marketing tools, technical solutions, and labellisation for tourist accommodations. (140 certified) [Prevention, mitigation]
Green Globe	All	1992	Industry organization	Global	Energy, water, waste...	International certification tool for sustainability Achievements: 10% water and energy saved. [Prevention, mitigation]
Green Key	All	1994	Industry associations and governmental institutions	Global, declined in several national groups	Energy, wastes, water, labor conditions	Supply chain, energy and water saving, wastes, awareness. +3000 Establishments. [Prevention, mitigation]

Indicators

GSTC Industry Criteria for Hotels	All	2016	NGO	Global	Land-use and, eco-habitat, working conditions, resources and wastes, cultural impact	Mitigation
European Tourism Indicators System for sustainable destination management (ETIS)	European Union	2013	European Commission	EU + overseas territories	Destination management, social and cultural impact	Mitigation

9 Examples of Good environmental practices

CRUISING SECTOR

NAME OF ACTION	LOCATION	DATE	ACTOR DRIVING THE INITIATIVE (NAME OF KEY ACTOR)	SCALE OF ACTION	KEY AREA OF ACTION	DESCRIPTION (OUTCOME)
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Specific taxes

<u>Environmental contribution</u>	Malta	2016	Government of Malta	National (Malta)	Destination management, contribution to environmental budgets.	Accommodation taxing, revenue dedicated to tourism infrastructures. [Regulation budget]
Eco Tourism Tax	Balearic Islands (Spain)	2016	Government of Balars	Regional (Balears, Spain)	Contribution to environmental budgets.	Varying rates based on the type of accommodation. Revenue used to compensate for the environmental impacts of tourism. [Regulation budget]

Financial incentives

Differentiated tariffs in Port	Barcelona, Spain	2020	Port authority of Barcelona	Port	Air emissions Noise.	Discounts to shipowners to promote improvements in vessels in terms of efficiency, the use of natural gas and batteries, and reducing atmospheric emissions. [Prevention Mitigation]
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Monitoring and transparency

Environmental Ship Index (ESI)	Global	2011	Industry-led (International Association of Ports and Harbors)	World	Air emissions Noise.	Indicator evaluating performance of ships in air emission reduction. Evaluation for NOX and SOX emissions, carbon emissions and PM emissions. Can also be used for port with OPS. [Mitigation]
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Legislation and Planning

Limitation of access on vessel size	Venice (Italy)	-	Government	City	Air pollution Dredging Erosion.	Prevention
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9 Examples of Good environmental practices

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NAME OF ACTION	LOCATION	DATE	ACTOR DRIVING THE INITIATIVE (NAME OF KEY ACTOR)	SCALE OF ACTION	KEY AREA OF ACTION	DESCRIPTION (OUTCOME)
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Legislation and Planning

Respect the City Dubrovnik Plan	Croatia	2017	City authorities of Dubrovnik	City	Overcrowding Environmental pressure.	Placing a cap on cruise tourism to 4000 + spread out arrivals. [Mitigation]
Cruise passenger rationing	Santorini (Greece)	2016	Government of Greece	City	Overcrowding Environmental pressure.	Implementation of a limit of cruise passengers during peak season. [Mitigation]

Infrastructure provision

<u>Onshore Power Supply (OPS) & clean mobility</u>	Barcelona, Spain	202 ongoing	Port Authority of Barcelona	Port	Air emissions Noise.	Renewal of the vehicle fleet with electric cars. Modernising public lighting with LED energy from renewable sources.
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Training

<u>Blue Wave Initiative</u>	Turkey	-	NGO (Travel Foundation)	Local	Waste, interaction with marine life, fuel and energy management.	Edition of training and sensitization material towards tourists and actors in English and Turkish. [Mitigation]
<u>Eco Navigation charter (La Méridionale)</u>	France	2018	Industry and governmental partnership	Local	Training Waste Emissions Biodiversity interactions.	Partnership MPA networks the French Governmental Agency for Biodiversity to diminish the impact of shipping, develop an internal stewardship and increase knowledge on impacts. [Mitigation]

ECOTOURISM

Legislation and Planning

<u>Posidonia regulation Balearic Islands</u>	Spain	2018	Government of Balearic Islands	Regional	Planning, Local management, conservation.	Regulation on the conservation of the oceanic posidonia in the Balearic Islands. Location of posidonia meadows in the nautical charts. Limit access and anchorage to recreational boats.
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9 Examples of Good environmental practices

ECOTOURISM

NAME OF ACTION	LOCATION	DATE	ACTOR DRIVING THE INITIATIVE (NAME OF KEY ACTOR)	SCALE OF ACTION	KEY AREA OF ACTION	DESCRIPTION (OUTCOME)
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Carrying Capacity

Diving tourism -Illes Medes	Spain (Catalunya)	2017	Government of Catalunya	Local	Planning, Local management, conservation.	Planning tools conserving the natural values, regulating tourism, recreational, sports, educational and scientists, as well as professional fishing.
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Labels and certifications

EUROPARC Sustainable Tourism Charter	Euro-Mediterranean countries	1995		International (European)	Land use planning, conservation (revenue), reduction of carbon footprint, pollution and resource use, accessibility quality of infrastructures, integrated management, local products promotion, training and capacity building.	Governance and certification tool for management of sustainable tourism in protected areas. Sustainable destination and protected areas, sustainable local tourism businesses within the charter area, and sustainable tour operators bringing visitors in the areas.
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Destination/Product development

Mediterranean Experience of Eco Tourism (MEET)	Mediterranean countries	2013	IUCN +	International Med	Management and coordination.	Promotion of low impact and sustainable tourism experience in natural areas of the Med region.
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Destination/Product development

World Surfing Reserve	Portugal	2009	Save the Waves Coalition	Global	Preserving the coastal environment, economics and direct action on the surf zone.	Selection of sites based on a series of specific criteria.
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eco-union

ECO-UNION

Eco-union is a citizen Think and Do tank working to accelerate the transition of our society towards sustainable development, with a strong focus in the areas of green and blue economy, responsible tourism, clean mobility, renewable energy and climate change.

www.ecounion.eu

ADEME (Financial Support)

ADEME is the French public agency active in the implementation of public policy in the areas of environment, energy and sustainable development, providing expertise and advisory services to businesses, local authorities and communities, government bodies and the public at large.

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Towards a Sustainable Blue Tourism in the Mediterranean

**Regional Governance, Environmental Management and Sustainable Recovery
of the Mediterranean Coastal and Maritime Tourism**